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1. Changes with respect to the description of work

No changes to deliverable scope.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is public and will be available at ELEVATE's website.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This deliverable evaluates how climate policy scenarios, i.e., scenarios considering current policies (CP), Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and Long-Term Strategies (NDC-LTS), compare to “Paris-aligned” scenarios. It focuses on the energy and economic (sectoral) system transformations, and the required action in the short-/mid-term, i.e., the next 15-20 years. Furthermore, it investigates how the timing of net-zero compares across scenarios, both regionally and globally.

We find that current policies and 2030 NDC pledges are not aligned with the Paris Agreement climate goal, whereas moving towards net-zero (NDC- LTS scenario) puts global ambition in better track with the Paris Agreement (1.7-1.9 °C of warming by 2100, i.e., in alignment with below 2 °C while efforts are still required to pursuing the 1.5 °C goal). Results on energy system transformation show that for reaching 1.5 °C the world needs to accelerate the deployment of solar and wind energy, while unabated fossil fuels need to be phased down/out. Geothermal and hydropower are relatively stable across scenarios. Bioenergy and carbon capture and storage show higher variance across models. The electricity sector is the main contributor to emission reductions across all models, while the AFOLU sector plays a consistent role in reducing emissions across models as well. Furthermore, different models exhibit different sectoral contributions, according to their individual characteristics. While for some models non-CO₂ emissions are a major contributor in total reductions, others project higher reductions in the transport and industry sectors.

Finally, in general, developed regions (e.g., EU, North America and Pacific OECD) should reach net-zero emissions earlier than the global average while developing regions (e.g., Africa, South and Southeast Asia) can reach net-zero emissions later in the century.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

See report below.

Version log

Version	Date	Released by	Nature of Change
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2	10-09-2025	Isabela Tagomori	Final version, for submission

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1. Introduction

“Paris-aligned” scenarios consist of scenarios that achieve the Paris Agreement’s climate goal of keeping the increase in global mean temperature well below 2 °C, and preferably at 1.5 °C, compared to pre-industrial levels (UNFCCC, 2015). This deliverable evaluates how climate policy scenarios (i.e., scenarios that consider existing policies and pledges) compare to “Paris-aligned” scenarios. It focuses on the energy and economic (sectoral) system transformations, and the required action in the short-/mid-term, i.e., the next 15-20 years. Furthermore, it investigates how the timing of net-zero compares across scenarios, both regionally and globally.

The scenarios used for this assessment were developed as part of WP2, Task 2.3 (Development of global and national climate policy pathways) (Dafnomilis, Hooijschuur, et al., 2024; Hooijschuur et al., 2024). Nine global Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) take part in this scenario exercise: AIM/Hub-Global, COFFEE, GCAM, GEM-E3, IMAGE, MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM, POLES, REMIND and WITCH. Further information about all participating models can be found in the IAMC Model Documentation Wiki (IAMC, 2024).

2. Scenario framework

For this analysis, the scenario framework follows the work conducted under WP2, Task 2.3 (Development of global and national climate policy pathways), evaluating three climate policy scenarios: 1) Current policies (CP); 2) Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC); and 3) NDCs to Long-Term Strategies (NDC-LTS). Furthermore, two cost-optimal “Paris-aligned” references are used: 1) a scenario aiming at 2 °C of global mean end-of-century temperature increase; and 2) a scenario aiming at 1.5 °C of global mean end-of-century temperature increase.

2.1. Current policies

Current policies are defined as currently implemented policies adopted by governments (through legislation) or non-binding targets backed by effective policy instruments. Ambitions and pledges are not included. The CP scenario in this analysis follows the Climate Policy Modelling Protocol (CPMP) with a cut-off date (for the inclusion of policies) of July 2023. After 2030/2040 (depending on the policy time frame), the level of ambition of countries remains the same until the end of the century. The CPMP is publicly available at the ELEVATE Zenodo Community (Dafnomilis, Hooijschuur, et al., 2024).

2.2. NDCs (Nationally Determined Contributions)

The NDC scenario assumes the implementation of countries NDCs by 2030. If a country has a conditional NDC, that was implemented. After 2030, the level of ambition of countries remains the same until the end of the century. Further information on NDC submissions can be found in the ELEVATE Modelling Protocol on Global and National Climate Pathways (Hooijschuur et al., 2024).

2.3. NDC-LTS (NDCs to Long-Term Strategies)

The NDC-LTS scenario assumes the implementation of the countries NDCs by 2030, and after 2030 assumes the implementation of their Long-Term Strategies, moving from 2030 emissions to reaching net-zero by the target year (e.g. for EU, the net-zero GHG target year is 2050). Further information on LTS (and net-zero pledges) can be found in the ELEVATE Modelling Protocol on Global and National Climate Pathways (Hooijschuur et al., 2024).

2.4. “Paris-aligned” scenarios

This study uses two “Paris-aligned” cost-optimal scenarios as reference: 1) 2 °C scenario (full century budget¹ of 1150 GtCO₂); and 2) 1.5 °C scenario (peak budget² of 650 GtCO₂ and full century budget of 400 GtCO₂). Both scenarios follow current policies until 2025.

3. International climate policy and the road to Paris

3.1. Well-below 2 °C

The Paris Agreement, in Article 2, states the goal to “holding the increase in global average temperature to well below 2 °C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels, recognizing that this would significantly reduce the risks and impacts of climate change” (UNFCCC, 2015).

Figure 1 shows the global emission pathways for the cost-optimal 2 °C and 1.5 °C scenarios.

¹ Full century budget between 2020 and 2100.

² Peak budget between 2020 and the time of net-zero.

Figure 1. Global emission pathways and temperature outcomes for the “Paris-aligned” cost-optimal scenarios (2 °C and 1.5 °C). Points show different models; colours show different scenarios.

Figure 2 shows the global emission pathways and the respective temperature outcomes for three climate policy scenarios: CP, NDC and NDC-LTS.

Figure 2. Global emission pathways and temperature outcomes for scenarios representing policies and pledges (CP, NDC and NDC-LTS). Points show different models; colours show different scenarios.

Our results corroborate earlier findings (Dafnomilis, den Elzen, et al., 2024; Meinshausen et al., 2022; Ou et al., 2021; Pianta & Brutschin, 2023; Rogelj et al., 2023;

UNEP, 2024; van Soest et al., 2021) that indicate that existing policies and 2030 NDC pledges are not aligned with the Paris Agreement climate goal, leading to increases in global mean temperature of 2.4–3.1 °C for CP, and 1.9–2.8 °C for the NDC scenario (i.e., if ambition beyond 2030 is not further strengthened). However, moving towards net-zero (as proposed in NDC-LTS) by around mid-century aligns global ambition with the Paris Agreement, leading to 1.7–1.9 °C. Nonetheless, while this brings global mean temperature increase to below 2 °C, further efforts are still needed to keep it at 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels.

3.2. Climate action in the short-/mid-term

The analysis of the global emission pathways shows that early action is crucial to achieving the mid- to long-term goals: emissions must reduce substantially between 2030 and 2050 (Figures 1 and 2). The assessment in this section will evaluate climate action needed in the short-/mid-term related to 1) the energy transition (focusing on energy sources); and 2) the sectoral transformations.

3.2.1. Energy transition

A transition in the energy system from carbon-intensive (fossil) to clean energy sources is required for achieving the Paris climate goals. Figure 3 presents primary energy changes compared to current levels a) in 2040; and b) in 2050, showing the range of models for all scenarios.

Our results³ show that the world needs to accelerate the deployment of solar and wind energy: under a 1.5 °C scenario solar deployment is projected to reach 2947 GW and wind 2440 GW, by 2050. Contrastingly, unabated fossil fuels need to be phased down/out, with projected retirements of 68 EJ/year for oil, 3169 GW for gas, and 4278 GW for coal. Other non-biomass renewables such as geothermal and hydropower are more stable across scenarios, with modest expansions in the short-/mid-term (178 GW and 269 GW by 2050, respectively), except for few model-specific outcomes (e.g., POLES is an optimistic outlier for geothermal, and COFFEE for hydropower). Bioenergy and carbon capture and storage (associated with biomass, gas or coal) are controversial, varying notably across models. Nonetheless, they could play a role in reaching the Paris goal with additions of approximately 50 EJ/year of biomass (27 EJ/year with CCS), 247 GW of gas with CCS, and 260 GW of coal with CCS, by 2050.

Current global long-term strategies (NDC-LTS) fall between the 1.5 °C and the 2 °C goals, reflecting a stronger expansion of most renewables, nuclear and carbon capture and storage technologies and a stronger phase down/out of fossil fuels, except for hydropower and unabated coal, which follow a trend more in line with the projections for the 2 °C scenario.

³ Model median, in EJ/year for biomass and oil, and in GW for other energy sources.

Figure 3. Change in primary energy compared to current levels a) in 2040; and b) in 2050. Points show different models; colours show different scenarios.

3.2.2. Sectoral transformations

Sectoral transformations are investigated through CO₂ emissions in five different sectors: AFOLU, buildings, electricity, industry and transport. Non-CO₂ emissions are grouped separately. Figure 4 presents the results for seven global IAMs (AIM/Hub-Global, COFFEE, GCAM, GEM-E3, IMAGE, MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM and POLES)⁴ across the three climate policy scenarios (CP, NDC and NDC-LTS).

Figure 4. GHG emission projections until 2050, CO₂ by sector and non-CO₂ separately, per scenario, per model.

The electricity sector is the main contributor for emission reductions across all models, as it is considered a 'low-hanging fruit' in short-term emission reductions. For

⁴ REMIND and WITCH did not report sectoral details for emissions.

most models, the implementation of NDCs results in slightly lower emissions compared to CP⁵, mostly coming from the power sector.

Moving from NDCs towards LTS (NDC-LTS) intensifies emission reductions by 2050. In this more stringent climate policy scenario (NDC-LTS), contributions from other sectors become more prominent, especially after 2030. However, different models exhibit different behaviour, according to their individual characteristics. For example, non-CO₂ emissions are a major contributor in total reductions in AIM/Hub-Global and GEM-E3, while transport and industry (except for GEM-E3) emissions remain relatively stable by 2050. Contrastingly, transport and industry emissions reduce noticeably in models such as IMAGE and POLES, while non-CO₂ emissions constitute the main part of their residual emissions in 2050. The AFOLU sector plays a bigger role in the NDC-LTS scenario for most models: emissions in the sector reduce significantly by 2050 in COFFEE, GCAM, GEM-E3 and POLES, even going to negative around 2035 in MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM. Finally, emissions in the buildings sector remain relatively stable across all models and scenarios to 2050, which is to be expected given that the sector operates on a much longer timescale than the others.

3.3. Timing of net-zero

Figure 5 shows the timing of net-zero for R10 regions (i.e., countries aggregated into 10 global regions), for NDC-LTS, and the 2 °C/1.5 °C scenarios, highlighting how they compare to the average global GHG timing in the 1.5 °C scenario.

⁵ Except for COFFEE and MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM, where NDC and NDC-LTS implementations are similar in the short-term.

Figure 5. Timing of net-zero greenhouse gases for ten global regions (R10), for the range of models, for the NDC-LTS, the 2 °C and the 1.5 °C scenarios, and the global average for the 1.5 °C scenario (in grey). Colours show different scenarios; “2100” includes 2100 or later.

For the model ensemble, global net-zero GHG emissions should be reached around 2080 to keep warming at 1.5 °C (model median, with some models reaching it earlier, around 2065, and other models later, 2100 or thereafter). In general, developed regions i.e., Europe, North America and Pacific OECD, and developing regions such as China+, Reforming Economies (Russia) and Latin America (including Brazil), should reach net-zero earlier than the global average. Contrastingly, for the same warming outcome, other developing regions such as South Asia (including India) and Southeast Asia, the Middle East and Africa reach net-zero much later, after 2090.

Current net-zero pledges are consistent with the overall 1.5 °C goal for regions such as Africa, South Asia (including India) and the Middle East. For regions like Europe and Latin America, while the regional result for NDC-LTS differs from net-zero years projected in the 1.5 °C scenario, current pledges from countries or groups of countries (e.g., the EU) within these regions are aligned with the corresponding climate goal. For example, the EU has a pledged GHG net-zero in 2050, which aligns with the 1.5 °C projections for the region. Similarly, Brazil has a 2050 GHG net-zero pledge, which aligns with the 1.5 °C projections for Latin America. Nonetheless, it’s important to note that for some major emitter economies such as China, India, and the EU, current net-zero pledges are hard to be achieved in IAMs (not feasible in some models), indicating that further climate action is required.

4. Final remarks

This report evaluates climate policy scenarios based on current policies and current pledges (NDCs and long-term strategies, such as net-zero pledges) and their alignment with the Paris Agreement climate goal. From both a global GHG emissions trajectory and the energy transition perspective, our results indicate that, while CP (warming in the range of 2.4-3.1 °C) and NDCs (warming in the range of 1.9-2.8 °C) are far from putting the world in a well below 2 °C path, NDC-LTS (warming in the range of 1.7-1.9 °C) represents a big step forward, falling within the 1.5 °C and 2 °C projections. Such outcomes are driven by a significant expansion of renewables, especially solar and wind power, and the phase down/out of unabated fossil fuels, with high agreement across models.

Timing of net-zero emissions shows that, in general, developed regions (e.g. EU, North America and Pacific OECD countries) should reach net-zero emissions earlier than the global average. Contrastingly, developing regions (e.g. Africa, South and Southeast Asia) can reach net-zero emissions later in the century. Current long-term strategies reflected in the NDC-LTS scenario do not reach net-zero emissions globally, given that not all nations have pledged to reach climate neutrality. Most major emitters, e.g. EU, Brazil, Japan, China, India and the USA (before the current administration withdrew from the Paris Agreement), have net-zero pledges aligned with the 1.5 °C goal. However, for some of these countries (e.g. China, India) some models indicate that current net-zero pledges are hard to achieve (not feasible), indicating they require further climate action.

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